

OPTIMIZATION OF METHODS OF DIAGNOSIS AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF LIVER DAMAGE IN CLOSED ABDOMINAL TRAUMAS

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Abstract Currently, there is an increase in the number of road traffic accidents and terrorist attacks, which naturally leads to an increase in both combined and isolated closed abdominal trauma [3, 6, 10, 11, 15]. At the same time, damage to parenchymatous organs in the structure of abdominal trauma makes up 56-66.8%. Data from scientific publications [1, 11, 13, 14] indicate that traumatic injuries to abdominal organs are accompanied by a high level of disability, and mortality remains unacceptably high, amounting to 30-44% with no tendency to decrease. Complicated course is observed in 37-45% of cases [1, 2, 4, 5, 7, 12].

Keywords: closed abdominal trauma, liver damage, combined trauma, diagnostics, treatment methods, endovideosurgical hemostasis, tamponade.

The aim of the study is to improve the results of diagnostics and treatment of patients with closed liver injuries by developing and implementing diagnostic and treatment algorithms in a multidisciplinary hospital.

Materials and methods. The analysis of the results of surgical treatment of 247 patients with closed abdominal trauma and liver damage hospitalized in the 1st emergency surgical department of Fergana branch of the Republican Scientific Center of Emergency Medical Care from 2010 to 2020 was carried out. The patients were aged from 17 to 78 years: up to 44 years old - 192 (77.7%) patients, from 45 to 60 years old - 44 (17.8%) patients, from 60 to 71 years old - 8 (3.2%) patients, over 75 - 3 (1.2%). Moreover, 78% were men.

All patients were divided into 2 groups depending on the time of hospitalization. The first group included patients from 2010 to 2015 (n = 117), the second - from 2016 to 2020 (n = 130).

Most of the patients were hospitalized within the first 6 hours from the moment of injury, which amounted to 195 (78.9%) patients; during the next 7-24 hours, 20 (8.1%) patients were delivered to the hospital; more than 24 hours later, 32 (13%) patients sought help. A total of 139 (56.3%) patients were delivered in a state of shock: stage 1 shock was noted in 58 (23.5%) cases; stage 2 shock was diagnosed in 45 (18.2%) observations; stage 3 shock was detected in 36 (14.6%) patients. 26 (10.5%) patients were delivered in a terminal state.

The X-ray method for blunt abdominal trauma was used in 161 (65.2%) cases. The sensitivity of the technique was only 28.5%. Ultrasound examination (US) of the abdominal organs was performed in 235 (95.1%) cases, which in addition to the clinical picture allowed us to assume liver damage in 219 patients. The sensitivity of the technique was 92.6%. Diagnostic laparoscopy was performed in 178 (72.1%) patients. In 162 (91% of diagnostic laparoscopies) cases, indications for laparotomy were made.

Results and discussion. In 14 (5.7%) cases, diagnostic laparoscopy revealed grade I – II liver injury with ongoing parenchymal bleeding, which was stopped using endovideosurgical

techniques. In 17 (6.9%) patients, liver injury without ongoing bleeding was diagnosed, which allowed us to limit ourselves to abdominal drainage. In 12 (4.9%) cases, diagnostic laparoscopy failed to reveal any injury due to damage to hard-to-reach liver segments. No specific clinical symptoms were detected in patients with closed abdominal trauma involving liver damage. The main reasons for the “blurring” of the clinical picture should be considered severe concomitant injury, damage to other anatomical areas, as well as exogenous intoxication, which was noted in 52 (21.1%) cases.

“Hard to reach” segments of the liver, according to G. Muller et K. Little [10], are not diagnosed during primary interventions in 3.7% of cases, especially in combination with damage to other abdominal organs. We noted damage to "hard-to-reach" liver segments in blunt abdominal trauma in 145 cases, which amounted to 58.7% of the total number of patients. During primary surgical intervention, liver damage was not detected in 18 (7.3%) patients, which in most cases was associated with the localization of the defect in segments 7–8 (13 observations), as well as combined damage to abdominal organs (5 cases). At the same time, in 10 observations in this category of patients, diagnostic laparoscopy was limited without control drainage of the abdominal cavity. Mortality in the group was 4 (1.6%) patients. The main reason for diagnostic errors was the refusal to revise the liver and place control drainage during diagnostic laparoscopy.

Combined liver damage was detected in 168 (68%) cases. Multiple damage was detected in 77 (31.2%) patients, which determined the greater severity of this type of damage and "masked" the clinical picture of liver injuries. Damage to the right lobe of the liver was noted in 208 (84.2%), and to the left lobe in 39 (15.8%) cases.

Damage to segments VI – VIII of the liver was dominant, amounting to a total of 170 (68.8%) patients. Most often, damage to abdominal organs was combined with chest trauma – 101 (40.9%) cases and with craniocerebral trauma – 67 (27.1%) patients.

It is known that for the diagnosis of liver damage, an objective assessment of the degree of organ damage and the severity of combined trauma is of great importance. To determine the most optimal treatment and diagnostic program and continuity in the provision of specialized surgical care, we used the scale for assessing the severity of multiple and combined trauma, the classification of liver damage according to E. Moore et al. [16], which distinguishes 6 degrees of damage. Based on the degree of liver damage according to the given classification, the patients were distributed as follows: degree I - 86 (34.8%); degree II - 79 (32%); degree III - 60 (24.3%); degree IV - 17 (6.9%); degree V - 5 (2%). We did not encounter degree VI damage. According to the VPK-MT scale, severe abdominal organ damage was noted in 128 (51.8%) cases, and extremely severe - in 119 (48.2%).

As a rule, treatment of liver damage is only surgical, although there are reports in the literature of spontaneous healing of small liver ruptures [16, 17].

In 114 (97.15%) cases in patients of group I, upper-mid-midline laparotomy was used as an access to the liver. In 7 (5.98%) cases, endovideosurgical access was performed, which allowed us to limit ourselves to drainage of the abdominal cavity in case of liver damage without ongoing bleeding. In case of liver damage of grades I and II, primary liver wound suturing was used in 78 (66.7%) cases. In case of more severe damage, liver defect tamponade was performed – 36 (30.8%) cases, and in 4 (3.4%) cases tamponade was supplemented by hepatopexy. In the presence of intramural hematoma of the gallbladder, in the overwhelming majority of cases, preference was

given to conservative management tactics. Subcapsular and intrahepatic hematomas were opened in 12 (10.3%) and 5 (4.3%) cases, respectively, and in 8 (6.8%) cases, conservative management tactics were chosen. In addition, concomitant damage to the abdominal organs was eliminated.

The following complications were noted when using this surgical tactic: subdiaphragmatic abscesses – 41 (35%); intrahepatic abscesses – 14 (12%); erosive bleeding – 16 (13.7%); posttraumatic cholecystitis – 12 (10.3%) observations, of which 11 patients subsequently required repeated surgical interventions. The complications that occurred were mainly of a combined nature.

Mortality in group 1 was 39 (33.3%), with the majority of patients having liver damage of grades II – IV – 9 (23.1%), 14 (38.5%) and 8 (20.5%), respectively. The causes of death were: injury incompatible with life (up to 24-hour mortality) – 5 (12.9%); brain dislocation – 4 (10.3%).

In 1 of 4 patients who died from brain dislocation, no clinical data for severe craniocerebral injury were detected upon admission, and the entire symptom complex manifested itself within the first 3 days from the moment of injury. Undoubtedly, in this group, late diagnosis of severe craniocerebral injury led to an unfavorable outcome. In addition, purulent-septic complications were noted in 8 (6.8%) cases and acute cardiovascular failure in 5 (4.3%) observations.

Analysis of the treatment results for patients in Group I prompted additional research, which resulted in the development and implementation of diagnostic and tactical algorithms for providing assistance to patients in a multidisciplinary hospital setting.

All patients of the second group were delivered to the operating room, where most diagnostic and therapeutic manipulations were performed. The diagnostic standard included: clinical and biochemical blood tests, coagulogram, general urine analysis, electrocardiogram, X-ray examination of the chest, pelvis, limbs (if indicated), ultrasound of the abdominal cavity, consultation with a traumatologist and neurosurgeon, therapist, CT of the brain, diagnostic laparoscopy.

In patients of group 2, laparotomy was also used as the main approach in 115 (88.5%) cases, but endovideosurgical approach was performed in 23 (17.7%) cases. In 94 (72.3%) cases, hemostasis was achieved by forming a primary suture of the liver wound, and in 6 (4.6%) patients the primary suture was supplemented with tamponade with a napkin. In 7 (5.4%) cases, liver resection was performed, which in 2 (1.5%) cases was completed by tamponade to achieve final hemostasis after resection. Opening of intrahepatic and subcapsular hematomas was performed in 8 (6.2%) and 18 (13.8%) cases, respectively, and in 9 (6.9%) cases, conservative management tactics were chosen. Tamponade of liver damage, as the main surgical technique, was used only in 10 (7.7%) cases and, as a rule, in patients with severe combined trauma within the framework of the « Damage tactic control ». In 3 (2.3%) cases, tamponade was supplemented by hepatopexy. In 16 (6.5%) patients, endovideosurgical hemostasis was achieved, and in 11 (8.5%) cases, diagnostic laparoscopy revealed liver damage without ongoing bleeding, which allowed us to limit ourselves to drainage of the abdominal cavity. In case of gallbladder injury, preference was given to active surgical tactics, which in 7 (5.4%) cases consisted of cholecystectomy or in 4 (3.1%) observations, cholecystostomy. Indications for the latter were: hematoma occupying less than 50% of the visible surface of the gallbladder wall, and / or concomitant damage to the pancreas or duodenum.

In addition to the difference in surgical tactics, other types of treatment were identical. The distribution of patients by gender, age, nature and severity of injury, timing of surgical intervention

from the moment of injury in both groups was representative, which made it possible to conduct a comparative analysis of the results of using different surgical tactics in these patients. The used treatment and diagnostic algorithm made it possible to reliably reduce the frequency of postoperative complications: subdiaphragmatic abscesses from 35% in group 1 to 17.1% in group 2; intrahepatic abscesses from 12% in group 1 to 2% in group 2; erosive bleeding from 13.7% in group 1 to 4.5% in group 2; posttraumatic cholecystitis from 10.3% to 3.6%, respectively. The introduction of CT of the brain into the examination standard upon admission made it possible to identify brain damage in 15 (22.4%) of 67 patients admitted to the clinic with a diagnosis of traumatic brain injury in the absence of clinical data.

Conclusions. Thus, the conducted studies show that in 31.2% of cases liver damage is multiple, and in 68% it is combined. In patients with combined head and abdominal trauma, mandatory CT of the brain allows to reduce mortality from edema and dislocation of the brain in traumatic brain injury from 10.3 to 4.9%. Endovideosurgical hemostasis is indicated for hemodynamically stable patients with severe abdominal organ injuries in isolated liver injuries of grades I - II. During laparotomy for grades I - III liver injury, primary liver wound suturing is indicated for hemodynamically stable patients with severe and extremely severe abdominal organ injuries. Atypical resection of the liver lobe is indicated for grades IV - V liver injury in patients with severe abdominal organ injuries, and is also acceptable for grade IV liver injury in hemodynamically stable patients with extremely severe abdominal organ injuries. Tamponade of liver wound within the framework of tactics « Damage control » is indicated for any liver damage in hemodynamically unstable patients with extremely severe damage to the abdominal organs. In case of damage to the gallbladder, cholecystectomy is indicated. An indication for cholecystostomy is a hematoma occupying less than 50% of the visible surface of the gallbladder wall and/or concomitant damage to the pancreas or duodenum. Conservative tactics for managing intrahepatic and subcapsular hematomas are acceptable if they are non-tense. The use of the proposed individual surgical tactics for closed abdominal trauma with liver damage has reduced the mortality rate from 33.3 to 17.1%.

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